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Anambra State Waste Management Agency (ASWAMA) And Environmental Sanitation In Anambra State Of Nigeria 2011-2022

¹Obiorah, Chiamaka Ugochukwu; ²Ikenna Mike Alumona (Ph.D) & Collins Ekene Okelue

Department of Political Science
Faculty of Social Sciences

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria

¹amakachukz@gmail.com; ²im.alumona@coou.edu.ng; ³ce.okelue@coou.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The rate of undiscerning dispose of refuse and careless handling of waste in Anambra State in particular has been undoubtedly alarming. It is on the basis of this that the study looked into Anambra State Waste Management Agency and Environmental Sanitation in Anambra State of Nigeria from 2011 to 2022. The study adopted a quantitative approach with longitudinal research design providing the methodological framework. Two research questions were answered while one research hypotheses guided the study in drawing logical conclusions. Data was sourced through primary and secondary means, including; textbooks, the commission's records, bulletins, newspapers, magazines, unpublished academic dissertations, journal papers, and seminar papers while quantitative descriptive analytical approach was deployed for the data analysis. Multi stage sampling techniques was used to select respondents from the targeted area of study. Based on the logical analysis, the study reported that the strategic methods that ASWAMA have been deploying for the application of waste management policies that promote environmental sanitation to include, but are not limited to: recycling; monthly sanitation; open dumping; collaboration with Operation Clean and Healthy Anambra (OCHA brigade), communities, and private contractors. The study further identified the issues affecting ASWAMA to include: lack of fund, dysfunctional environment court, inadequate and dysfunctional operation machine, poor attitude of residents as regards to waste disposal, proliferation of illegal structures along drainages, indiscriminate dumping of wastes, shortage of staff, lack of proper data on waste disposal etc. The study recommends among others that government should provide more waste facilities and technology for ASWAMA to deliver their work effectively.

Keywords: Anambra State, Waste Management Agency and Environmental Sanitation

INTRODUCTION

Environmental sanitation is a global task that is premised on the need to safeguard the totality of man's surrounding. It entails the propositions made to ensure that the environment is ripped off any ugly experience that is capable of threatening its safety and sustainability, such as climate change, global warming, pollutions, and undiscerning dispose of waste among others. It is understandable that a healthy and safe environment plays a positive role in ensuring that life continues to exist in a manner that is worth living. The global campaigns against the activities of man that is capable of causing degradation are

efforts made to safe guard the environment from making man vulnerable. These efforts are integral part of environmental sanitation measures to ensure a livable environment. Human environment needs to be kept clean, the 7th goal of the millennium development is to ensure a clean environmental sustainability. The pursuit of environmental sustainable well-being as identified by the United Nations Environmental Program (UNEP, 2024), however waste generation is indispensable as long as man is in existence.

To experience a healthy and livable environment, the quality of air we breathe, water we drink, sound we hear, and heat we feel, have to improve to a commendable level. This is supported by Amadi and Alapiki (2019), emphasized that federal and state environmental sanitation efforts are targeted at attaining air quality, water quality, waste management, and land conservation etc. In other to achieve this objective of a safe environment, the federal government of Nigeria promulgated decree 48 for the establishment of a Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) on 30th December 1988 Nwakoby et al. (2020). The decree or law on environmental sanitation required specific policy measures that make for positive and realistic planning to attain its goals.

Environmental policy contains government rules and regulations that are directed towards safeguarding the environment. The policies at federal level in Nigeria require that a number of complementary policies, strategies and management approaches to be put in place by state governments, governmental agencies, organizations, communities and other stakeholders to ensure that environmental sanitation policies are achieved (Amadi & Alapiki, 2019). This provided Anambra state the avenue to implement policies aimed at safeguarding the environment. The state understand that environmental sanitation is a necessity that calls for serious commitment and actions, and has made remarkable efforts ensuring that the increasing waste generated in the state is effectively managed.

Waste management in Anambra State, especially in Awka and Onitsha, is increasing drastically as heaps of refuse are found at various places in the aforementioned cities of Anambra State (Otti, 2011). In response to this, Anambra State government through the ministry of environment promulgated policies geared towards making the environment livable for all. The policies are meant to be fully implemented to guarantee a safe, healthy and livable environment with absence or minimal environmental threats. In a bid to protect the environment from degenerating due to undiscerning disposal of waste, the State have witnessed three different agencies, namely: Anambra State Environmental Sanitation Authority (ASESA), established in 1985 to protect the environment from problem caused by solid waste generation and poor handling of waste it operated from 1985 to 1998 and was dissolved due to they failed to change the looks of the state.; Anambra State Environmental Protection Agency (ANSEPA), established 1998 and was charged with the obligation of conducting environmental sanitation and to implement strict observation of environmental policy in Anambra State and were badly criticized due to failure to meet up with public expectations and the current Anambra State Waste Management Agency (ASWAMA) which was established in 2011. In view of the foregoing, Nnaji, Udunze and Dimukeje (2017), stated that the government of Anambra State through her environmental sanitation agency known as Anambra State Waste Management Agency (ASWAMA), and the defunct ASESA and ANSEPA were charged with the responsibility to ensure that environmental policy is implemented by engaging campaigns to create awareness, educate and sensitize the citizenry on the dangers of undiscerning disposal of refuse in the society. The enlightenment campaigns and other policy programmes, if effectively implemented by the agencies could have impacted the environment very well. Whether ASWAMA, as the latest environmental sanitation agency in the state have been effective in its efforts or not is an aspect that needs to be explore and verify. The heaps of refuse that is found across different parts of the State, raises an eye-brow against ASWAMA's role and efforts at liberating the state from her poor environmental outlook. It is understandable that the public need to be well informed and properly oriented on all implementable environmental sanitation policies of government, perhaps, to seek their cooperation with the agency in achieving their objectives.

According to Ihueze and Chukwumuanya (2015), they emphasized that ASWAMA is charged with the obligation of making sure that the environmental policies is achieved under the state ministry of environment, and with collaboration with private contractors to jumpstart its service delivery to the public. In doing this, the agency has been making efforts at the provision of dumping sites, placement of

collection bins at various intervals within reach, provision of incinerators, and sanctioning of some defaulters. This is supported by Nwakoby, Okoye and Chukwurah (2020), who stated that the agency is making effort by providing waste bins, vans, sweepers, and dumping sites to ensure that the environmental policy is implemented. These efforts are not enough in bringing about the kind of environment the government and the public are dreaming about, perhaps, due to obvious challenges the agency is believed to be experiencing.

In spite of the efforts which are believed to have been made towards turning environmental policies from paper to reality, there is high rate of erosion sites, excessive waste generation, improper disposal of liquid waste, poor public environmental awareness, lots of illegal structures along drainages, dumping of wastes into gutters, roadsides, drainages, bushes, streams, and several other places (Okoye, 2017), as well as indiscriminate dumping of wastes at various locations in the areas under study (Amalu & Ajake, 2014). These issues are believed to be as a result of lack in funding, poor staff management, poor attitude of the public, uncontrolled urbanization, spread of offensive odor, diseases and awful look of Awka, Ekwulobia, Nnewi and Onitsha.

The problem, according to Habitat (2012), is caused by lack of well-planned market sites and inadequate well-identified sanitary landfill for waste disposal, poor method for handling sewage, lack of record keeping as regards to waste. The unwanted situation in the aforementioned towns has been truly worrisome to the state government, her agency, ASWAMA, local communities, organizations, residents and businesses. Most literature had paid more attention to the method of waste management; Environmental problems of urbanization and waste management; organizational structure of ANSEPA and other waste management agencies in the State; as well as history of waste disposal in the State. However, in relation to Anambra State, previous scholars have neglected the aspect of environmental sanitation that border on assessment of government policies on the environment; the role ASWAMA play in the initiation and execution of public policies for environmental sanitation, as well as exploring the fundamental factors that have limited ASWAMA from effectively implementing environmental sanitation policies in Anambra State. It is on the basis of this gap that this study is set out to investigate the impact of Anambra State waste management agency on environmental sanitation in Anambra State.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Some studies have been conducted by scholars on environmental sanitation. Examples of such specific studies include Falade (2012) on Environmental sanitation and Health concern associated with open dumping of waste. Amalu and Ajake (2014) carried out an investigation on appraisal of solid waste management practice in Enugu. Otti (2011), did a study on a model for solid waste management in Anambra state, Foyeke Omoboye .I. and Adedoyin Oluwatoyin O et al.(2024) researched on assessing the impact of environmental awareness on sanitation in Ekiti State. Yoade, A.O (2019) carried out a study on environmental sanitation practice in sub-sahara Africa among others.

Despite the contributions made by these researchers and the examination of other literature, shows that most of them were in urbanization and environmental sanitation. Some literature looked at solid waste as a key response to this gap; this study is an effort to concentrate on how Anambra State waste management agency manages environmental sanitation. The organization is specifically dedicated to establishing ASWAMA and matters related to creating laws for waste management and its implementation. However, this research concentrated on the part that has to with urban waste management. It is truism that waste generation is normal and inevitable and has become a danger to urban environment. It is not unusual that the health of the urban dwellers is at risk due to poor or unmanaged environmental sanitation.

However, it was revealed that ANSEPA was dissolved because the environmental sanitation laws were not strictly observed and needed urgent improvement by providing adequate funds, good operating environment, adequate equipment etc. Instead of the government to solve the problems of ANSEPA rather another agency was established in 2011 which is ASWAMA. Moreover, there is high rate of epidemics and diseases, like cholera, typhoid, diarrhea, malaria, bronchitis, asthma which usually result from delay in disposing of waste in a particular area. There is indiscriminate dumping of waste in gutters, road side, stream, and other unauthorized places. Unfortunately, in spite of all the powers given to ASWAMA, there are some factors that limiting them from effectively delivering their work such as

indiscriminate dumping of waste at strategic places like Agu Awka Market, New parts Market Nkpor, Onitsha Owerri Road, Eke Awka axis, no good mechanics, no state recycling plants, poor funding, inadequate staff among others.

All these deficiencies on the environment has prompted to undertake this study. The study on how ASWAMA has managed environmental sanitation policy in Anambra state and factors that has limited ASWAMA from effectively delivering their task and made recommendation for a healthy environment.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the impact of Anambra State Waste Management Agency on environmental sanitation in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine how Anambra State Waste Management Agency (ASWAMA) has managed environmental sanitation in Anambra State.
2. Account for the factors that are constraints of ASWAMA in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. How has ASWAMA managed environmental sanitation in Anambra State?
2. What are the constraints of ASWAMA in environmental sanitation in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

This null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the Mean responses of ASWAMA and the members of the public on how ASWAMA has managed environmental sanitation in Anambra State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted longitudinal research design for this study. The area of the study is Anambra state. The population of the study comprised 2,000 people. 1,000 people in Awka south and 1,000 people in Onitsha south. This made up of the entire staff of ASWAMA and members of the public for both Awka south and Onitsha south. The sample size is 600 respondents drawn across the 2 major cities of Anambra State, namely: 300 respondents in Awka south and 300 respondents in Onitsha south. Multistage sampling technique was used for this study. The data were collected using mix method. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents with the help of three research assistants. A total of 650copies of the questionnaire was produced, and 300 copies distributed at first in Awka south and 300 in Onitsha south. The extra 50 copies will be set aside to replace any distributed copy that may be lost or mutilated due to possible limitations from the respondents. The instruments were validated by a research expert. A lecturer from Measurement and Evaluation, Department Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha formula and the reliability coefficient is 0.890 and is considered excellent and appropriate for the study. Data were analyzed using quantitative Descriptive method of analysis. Therefore, mean and standard deviation were used for data analysis while T-test was adopted in for the test of Hypotheses.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

4.1.1 Research Question One: How ASWAMA managed environmental sanitation in Anambra state? Awka south LGA.

S/N	Item statement	X	SD	Remarks
1.	ASWAMA are well equipped to deliver their task.	2.41	0.32	Disagreed
2.	ASWAMA are not doing very well in terms of refuse disposal.	2.42	0.35	Disagreed
3.	ASWAMA do not keep the state very neat regularly.	2.45	0.31	Disagreed
4.	The environmental court is not functioning effectively.	2.44	0.29	Disagreed
5.	Private contractors are not doing their best.	2.44	0.29	Disagreed

Onitsha south

S/N	Item statement	X	SD	Remarks
1.	ASWAMA are well equipped to deliver their task.	2.34	0.25	Disagreed
2.	ASWAMA are not doing very well in terms of refuse disposal.	2.58	0.31	Agreed
3.	ASWAMA do not keep the state very neat regularly.	2.60	0.35	Agreed
4.	The environmental court is not functioning effectively.	2.63	0.38	Agreed
5.	Private contractors are not doing their best.	2.81	0.51	Agreed

4.1.2 Research Question Two: *What are the constraints of ASWAMA in environmental sanitation in Anambra State?*

Awka south LGA.

S/N	Item statements	X	SD	Remarks
1.	Poor funding of ASWAMA by the government.	2.68	0.58	Agreed
2.	Shortage of staff strength.	2.71	0.61	Agreed
3.	Lack of functioning machine for the evacuation of waste.	3.20	0.72	Agreed
4.	Unseriousness in the punishment of defaulters.	2.52	0.53	Agreed
5.	Inadequate data on population of an area for proper and timely waste disposal.	2.65	0.52	Agreed

Onitsha south

S/N	Item statements	X	SD	Remarks
1.	Poor funding of ASWAMA by the government.	2.56	0.22	Agreed
2.	Shortage of staff strength.	2.68	0.35	Agreed
3.	Lack of functioning machine for the evacuation of waste.	2.69	0.32	Agreed
4.	Unseriousness in the punishment of defaulters.	2.58	0.35	Agreed
5.	Inadequate data on population of an area for proper and timely waste disposal.	2.78	0.38	Agreed

4.2 T-test of Research Hypothesis

In testing the hypotheses, if P-value of the t-test is less than or equal to 0.05 (alpha levels), null hypothesis will not be accepted. Put in another way, null hypothesis should not be accepted, if t-test calculated is greater than t-test critical. And, if otherwise, P-value of the t-test is greater than the alpha levels, null hypothesis should be accepted. On the other hand, accept the null hypothesis, if t-test critical is greater than t-test calculated.

Again, for research question, any item whose mean (\bar{x}) is equal to or above 2.50 is remarked agreed or large extent while items with mean (\bar{x}) that is less than 2.50 is considered or will be remarked as disagreed or low extent. That means with 4 points rating scale $1+2+3+4=10/4=2.50$.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of ASWAMA and members of the public on how ASWAMA has managed environmental sanitation in Awka south.

Table 4.1.1 T-test analysis of data on Mean rating of ASWAMA and members of the public in Awka south

Summary $P \leq 0.05$

Variable	\bar{X}	SD	df	significant	Remark
ASWAMA	12.15	16.57			
Members of the Public	12.13	17.00	298	0.41	not significant.

The above table shows that the significant value of 0.41 is greater than 0.05 of significant. The result further reveals that, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of ASWAMA and members of the public on how ASWAMA managed environmental sanitation in Anambra State. Therefore, the hypotheses of 20 significant difference 15 was accepted.

Table 4.1.2 T-test analysis of data on mean rating of ASWAMA and members of the public in Onitsha south.

Summary $P \leq 0.05$

Variable	\bar{X}	SD	df	significant	Remark
ASWAMA	13.16	15.53	298	0.42	not significant.
Members	13.17	16.52			

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of ASWAMA and the members of the public on how ASWAMA managed environmental sanitation in Onitsha south.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The above table 4.1.1 shows the mean and standard deviation in response to how ASWAMA managed environmental sanitation in Anambra state. It is in line with Ademiluyi and Odugbesan (2008); Afon (2006) emphasized that adequate sanitary practice has not been ensured, that they are characterized by lack of basic amenities and poor sanitation habits. Akapbio (2012) made it clear that general access to environmental sanitation facilities and services remains very poor. It is also in line with Aina (2006) observes that ignorance, negligence and lack of law to punish sanitary offenders. He suggested that awareness should be created among occupants for them to know the dangers of indiscriminate dumping of refuse.

The table 4.1.2 above shows the mean and standard deviation of the response of what factors accounts for the constraints of ASWAMA in Anambra state. It is in line Zerbock (2003), solid waste weakness has been attributes to lack of logistics and financial management, people's attitude towards waste disposal should not be ignored. It is also in line with Sirdhar (2010) that inadequate funding important factor militating or acting as a major problem of waste disposal. The cost of purchase and maintenance of vehicle involved in the collection and disposal of waste has risen so high that many sanitation agencies cannot afford to get them. It is also in line with Ania (2006) emphasized that low level of technology in waste management is one of the major problem of managing waste.

Summary of the Finding

The study finding is summarized as follow:

1. The study reported that the strategic methods that ASWAMA have been deploying for the implementation of waste management policies that promote environmental sanitation to include, but are not limited to: recycling; monthly sanitation; open dumping; collaboration with Operation Clean and Healthy Anambra (OCHA brigade), communities, and private contractors.
2. The study further identified the issues affecting ASWAMA to include: lack of fund, dysfunctional environment court, inadequate and dysfunctional operation machine, poor attitude of residents as regards to waste disposal, proliferation of illegal structures along drainages, indiscriminate dumping of wastes, shortage of staff, lack of proper data on waste disposal etc.

CONCLUSION

The study was able to capture the strategic methods at the disposal of ASWAMA for the implementation of waste management policies that promote environmental sanitation, including, but are not limited to: recycling; monthly sanitation; open dumping; collaboration with OCHA brigade, Miss Anambra Beauty Pageant, communities, and private contractors. The study established the connection and the influencing factors between the variables, ASWAMA's methods of waste management (independent/predictor variables) and environmental sanitation (dependent/criterion variable).

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the argument and analysis the study made the following recommendations.

1. ASWAMA as the latest environmental agency should be given all the necessary waste management facilities and technology they need in other to deliver their task effectively.
2. Environmental court should be made functional for the punishment of the defaulter without fear or favor.
3. ASWAMA should be adequately funded by the government to motivate the agency for service delivery.
4. Keeping of proper data on waste disposal of a particular area should be encouraged to avoid indiscriminate dumping of waste especially in the area under study.

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